

EARTH SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF THE ZHANASEMEYSKY FORESTRY "SEMEY ORMANY"

Shogelova N.,

*Master of Technical Sciences,
International Educational Corporation,
Assistant Professor (Kazakhstan, Almaty)*

Sartin S.,

*Candidate of Physical and Mathematical Sciences,
North Kazakhstan University named after Manash Kozybayev,
Associate Professor (Kazakhstan, Petropavlovsk)*

Omirezhanova Z.

*Candidate of Technical Sciences,
International Educational Corporation,
Associate Professor (Kazakhstan, Almaty)*

Abstract

Currently, the situation around forest management is unfavorable for the preservation of the total mass of forests. In general, there are often facts without control logging, incomplete restoration of forests, lack of operational information about the state of individual forest fund allotments and many smaller problems. In the development strategy of our country "Kazakhstan - 2050", the new political course of the established state highlights the process of digitalization of society. During the implementation of the project, it is planned to use GIS technology for the transition to full digitalization of forestry activities on the example of the Zhanasemeysky forestry "Semey Ormany". This will significantly reduce the influence of the human factor on the planning of the logging process and the restoration of forests.

Keywords: forest management, remote sensing of the earth, forest.

Currently, the situation around forest management is unfavorable for the preservation of the total mass of forests. In general, there are often facts without control logging, incomplete restoration of forests, lack of operational information about the state of individual forest fund allotments and a large number of smaller problems.

This situation may soon lead to a catastrophic ecological situation associated with the desertification of lands previously covered with forest. As well as the extremely unfavorable economic situation associated with the lack of a reserve forest fund for timber harvesting.

According to the satellite survey data, only during the period from 1995 to 2002, fires in the forests of the Irtysh region destroyed 162 thousand hectares of pine forests, which is 34% of their area. From 1997 to 2001, pine trees on an area of 17,988 hectares were killed by fire in only one of the nine forest districts [1].

Since the establishment of the state forest natural reserve "Semey Ormany" for the period 2003 – 2013, 735 violators have been brought to administrative responsibility for illegal logging, with fines in the amount of 10 million 305 thousand tenge, 89 criminal cases have been initiated, 688 violators have been charged with damage in the amount of 56 million 590 thousand tenge. For the period from 2017 to 2019, 382 offenses were registered, 15 facts of illegal logging were revealed. In 2021, 49 facts of illegal felling of trees and shrubs were revealed, for which 6 pre-trial investigations were launched and 43 violators were brought to administrative responsibility [2].

A similar situation is observed in many regions of the Republic of Kazakhstan, where active forest management is carried out [3].

An analysis of existing and implemented state programs for planting and restoring forests indicates the need to create electronic vector maps using free software applications and develop a model of effective forest management.

In the development strategy of our country "Kazakhstan - 2050", the new political course of the established state highlights the process of digitalization of society [4]. Rational nature management implies the optimal solution of environmental problems facing the territory, which arise as a result of various economic measures that have a direct or indirect impact on the environment. Usually, such impacts are destructive to the vegetation of the developed territory and contribute to anthropogenic dynamic processes. In some cases (for example, various types of forest management and agriculture) this is due to the direct use of plant resources: forest resources (wood, pine nuts, wild flora, etc.), steppe and meadow resources (hayfields and pastures), etc. In other cases, vegetation is affected by man-made and household emissions from industrial enterprises and residential areas. In addition, it is affected by the pyrogenic factor associated with targeted (man-made) burnout, usually used in traditional land use, or non-targeted forest and steppe fires. They are usually of anthropogenic origin and are caused by human activities: tourism, outdoor recreation, accidental use of plant resources, etc. [5].

One of the main tasks facing the forest nature reserve is the preservation of the ribbon pine forests

protected within its borders, which play an environment-forming role in the East Kazakhstan Irtysh region. The state of forest ecosystems is affected by fires, pests and diseases of the forest, poaching and logging.

Zhanasemeiskoye forestry is located on the territories of the GLPR "Semey Ormany" and has an area of 77,746 hectares. Protection of forests from unauthorized logging and hunting on the territory of the forestry is carried out by the forces of the service for the protection of natural complexes and objects, as well as by state inspectors directly on the territory of the reserve. The entire area is divided into blocks, the

average area of which is 100 hectares. State inspectors are assigned to the blocks, who constantly monitor their condition. Round-the-clock surveillance is conducted at checkpoints. The territory of the reserve is periodically patrolled by operational groups.

Figure 1 shows a part of the schematic map reflecting the spatial location of the taxable allotments, the qualitative structure of the lands and plantings of the forest fund of the forestry. It was created on the forestry plan by coloring the taxable allotments of the lands covered with forest vegetation according to the prevailing breeds and age groups. Other categories of forest fund lands are represented by conventional signs.

Fig.1 – Blocks on the map of Zhanasemeysky forestry

The implementation of forest monitoring requires the involvement of a wide range of means of obtaining information, an important place is given to space remote sensing systems. Quantitative and qualitative characteristics of forests continuously change during the natural development of biogeocenoses and under the influence of various anthropogenic and natural factors: its composition changes, borders migrate.

The degradation of forests is particularly dangerous in terms of quality, since in many cases low-value deserts or clearings arise in the areas of harems formed as a result of fires and subsequently cleared of burnt forest. This problem is the most urgent for the Abad region, since forests here play a leading role in protecting the territory from dust storms, slowing down the processes of erosion and deflation. In addition, the ribbon forests stretching across the entire territory of the Abai region are relict, as they grow on the sandy sediments of the ancient runoff valley, where the processes of desertification and prevailing winds led to the formation of Aeolian landforms (dunes), which are very well deciphered inside forests in satellite images due to the characteristic wavy structure and crescent shape.

The study is to assess the possibility of identifying and mapping the consequences of large forest fires with the calculation of their parameters based on remote sensing materials. Solving this problem by other means (ground and aerial) is associated with significant costs for obtaining the necessary data. Space information

makes it possible to quickly solve environmental and environmental problems.

According to the satellite survey data, only during the period from 1995 to 2002, fires in the forests of the Irtysh region destroyed 162 thousand hectares of pine forests, which is 34% of their area. From 1997 to 2001, pine trees on an area of 17,988 hectares were killed by fire in only one of the nine forest districts.

The volume of illegally cut down trees for the period 2010-2012 and for the first half of 2013 amounted to 2.7 thousand cubic meters, damage was caused in 17.2 million tenge, of which only 2.6 million were reimbursed. Only during the inspection by the prosecutor's office, 15 facts of illegal logging of 1,153 pine trees with a total volume of more than 150 cubic meters with damage amounting to 1 million 664 thousand 407 tenge were revealed. In 2013, 10 cases of illegal logging were detected, with a total volume of 239 cubic meters of felled wood, with the amount of damage of 1 million 811 thousand tenge. For the period from 2017 to 2019, 382 offenses were registered, 15 facts of illegal logging were revealed. In 2021, 49 facts of illegal felling of trees and shrubs were revealed, for which 6 pre-trial investigations were launched and 43 violators were brought to administrative responsibility.

References

1. Otchet o deyatel'nosti RGU «GLPR «Semej ormany» za 2021 god. – Semej 2022. <http://semej-ormany.kz>

2. Sajt media portala Azattyq ruhy [Elektronnyj resurs]. – Astana; 2022. . – Rezhim dostupa : rus.azattyq-ruhy.kz, svobodnyj.
3. Ajnabekov M.S. Sovremennoe sostoyanie lesnogo hozyajstva Respubliki Kazahstan // Materialy Mezhdunarodnoj nauchno-prakticheskoy konferencii «Lesnaya nauka Kazahstana: dostizheniya, problemy i perspektivy razvitiya», posvyashchennoj 60-letiyu sozdaniya KazNIILHA. – SHCHuchinsk., 2017. – S.13-25.
http://kazniilha.kz/public/files/2019/9/12/120919_183414_schuchinsk-2017.pdf
4. Strategiya «Kazahstan-2050»: novyj politicheskij kurs sostoyavshegosya gosudarstva, Poslanie Prezidenta Respubliki Kazahstan – Lidera Nacii N.A. Nazarbaeva narodu Kazahstana. - Astana, 2012, dekabr' -14.
5. Shogelova, N., Sartin, S., Zveryachenko, T. (2022). Devising recommendations based on a comprehensive assessment of the soil-geobotanical condition of land plots for executing afforestation activities. Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies, 2 (10 (116)), 30–41. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15587/1729-4061.2022.255054>